

three N levels in a randomized block design with four replications. P and K (17.5 kg P, 33 kg K/ha) were constant for all treatments, including control.

Chemical analysis established 4% N content of azolla, based on dry weight. Azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha at transplanting, with 3.5 kg P/ha, recorded a fresh weight of 5 t/ha at incorporation 20 d after transplanting.

In the wet season, yields with N fertilizer were consistently higher than that of control (see table).

Yield with fresh azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha with 3.5 kg P/ha and incorporated 20 d after inoculation were equal to yields with 5 t fresh azolla/ha incorporated before planting.

In the dry season, yields with 90 kg N/ha were significantly higher than in all other treatments. Azolla at 5 t/ha yielded 0.6 t/ha more than control.

The actual benefit of azolla in combination with fertilizer was rather inconsistent. But azolla alone showed significantly higher yields than control. This study suggests alternative fertilizer strategies when chemical fertilizers are scarce or expensive. □

Effect of azolla alone and in combination with N fertilizers on rice yield.^a Orissa, India, 1983.

Treatment per hectare	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Difference
<i>Wet season</i>		
90 kg N	3.7	1.8
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla	3.2	1.3
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.2
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.6	0.7
5 t azolla inoculated and incorporated at 20 DT ^b	2.6	0.7
Control	1.9	—
CD (0.05)	0.2	—
CV (%)	6	—
<i>Dry season</i>		
90 kg N	3.8	2.0
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
10 t azolla + 60 kg N	3.4	1.6
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.3
10 t azolla	3.1	1.3
30 kg N	3.0	1.1
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.8	0.9
5 t azolla	2.4	0.6
Control	1.8	—
CD (0.05)	0.1	—
CV (%)	4	—

^aMeans of 3 yr, 1983-86. ^bDays after transplanting.

Effect of gypsum and pyrite with different moisture regimes on sodic soil improvement and rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of adding 7.25 meq gypsum/100 g soil (50% G.R.) and pyrite equivalent to gypsum on sulfur basis at 3 moisture regimes (continuous saturation [CS], continuous flooding [CF], and alternate saturation and flooding [ASF]) on the improvement of sodic soil and on yield in a pot with 3 replications. Soil was highly sodic, with pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 95, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.45 meq/100 g soil, organic C 0.22%, CaCO₃, 2.75%, CEC 10.0

meq/100 g soil, and gypsum requirement 14.5 meq/100 g soil.

Gypsum and pyrite were added to soil in 10-kg glazed clay pots 2 wk before transplanting 30-d-old Pusa 2-21 seedlings. The moisture regimes were maintained from transplanting to crop maturity. Urea at 80 ppm N and zinc sulfate at 4.5 ppm Zn were applied — half the N and all the Zn at transplanting, the remaining N topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

Gypsum was better than pyrite in improving soil and yield of rice at all three moisture regimes. While CF proved more effective when gypsum was applied, ASF did better with pyrite (Table 1, 2). Growing of rice under CF facilitated greater sodic soil improvement. □

Table 1. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on soil pH and ESP after rice harvest. Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	pH (1:2) soil water			ESP		
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite
Continuous saturation	10.40	9.20	9.70	81.5	41.2	51.8
Alternate saturation – flooding	10.35	9.00	9.40	78.4	36.1	48.5
Continuous flooding	10.35	8.80	9.90	79.7	25.4	65.2

Table 2. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on rice grain yield.^a Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	Grain yield (g/pot)			
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Mean
Continuous saturation	1.10	12.67	5.77	6.51
Alternate saturation – flooding	1.47	14.87	8.40	8.24
Continuous flooding	1.93	18.40	4.13	8.15
Mean	1.50	15.31	6.10	

^aCD at P = 0.05: amendments = 0.72, moisture regimes = 0.72, amendments × moisture regimes = 1.25.

Availability to wetland rice of nitrogen from cattle manure

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Mineralization and availability of N from organic manure will be affected by its C-to-N ratio, soil management, and climatic conditions. Since only a part of organic N will be mineralized during the

growing season of rice, a residual effect of manures is expected in the following crop. We compared the availability of N from cattle manure with urea N to wetland rice. Residual effect was evaluated in a following wheat crop.

Soil of the experimental field was a Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.6, 0.34% organic C, 0.05% total N, and a water percolation rate of 4.5 mm/h. Treatments were 4 rates of N (0, 60, 120,